
Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Patterns of bandicoot rat damage to deep-water rice in Bangladesh

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In deepwater rice areas in Mirjapur Upazilla, Bangladesh, *Bandicota indica* (the greater Indian bandicoot rat) and *B. bengalensis* (the lesser bandicoot rat) cause substantial damage to rice crops. In late Aug and early Sep, when floodwater is near peak depth and rice is in the elongation stage, rats attack the top

shoots of rice plants, next to the node above water level. Leaf sheaths are bitten open for 2.5 to 4.0 cm and the top of the growing stem is eaten, after which the terminal leaf yellows and dies, providing a visual clue to rat damage in the field. Compensatory tillering begins just below the damaged node. On casual examination, dead shoots resemble rice stem borer damage.

Fields with *B. indica* damage were located as far as 500 m from the nearest exposed high ground. *B. indica* remained in areas of water hyacinth and where field debris, left after harvest, floated to the surface and formed a mat where rats could keep out of water.

Rats also constructed resting platforms of cut rice tillers in the fields. Some platforms were 50 × 50 cm and stood 3 to 4 cm above the water surface. Woven rat nests also were found attached to emerging rice tillers. One nest was roughly oval, 22 × 35 cm on top and 15 cm deep.

B. indica apparently lives in the flooded deepwater rice fields from before peak flood until after harvest. Population distribution in the fields is not related to distance from the nearest exposed high ground. During flood stage, extensive poison baiting in water hyacinth and floating field debris considerably reduced rat damage. □

Soil and crop management

A simple planting rod for population maintenance in rice fields

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Optimum rice plant population must be maintained for high grain yield. We designed a simple, efficient, and economic tri-planting rod (see figure) to guide spacing of transplanted rice.

The planting rod consists of two 50 × 25-cm wooden frames with 2 pegs for fixing the frames into the soil. Holes are spaced at 10, 15, and 20 cm in the lower part of the frame, so that 1.5 cm × 3.6-m aluminum rods can be inserted according to the space required between rows. The rods are secured to the frame by nails and are marked at 10-cm intervals with black paint for the between-plant spacing within the row. The planting rod weighs about 2.6 kg, making it easy to move.

With this planting rod, 26 persons can transplant 1 ha in 20 h.

The planting rod gives these advantages:

- optimum population/unit area is

Tri-planting rod for transplanting rice, Tamil Nadu, India.

- maintained;
- rows are uniform;
- the 0.3-m check row between the 2 blocks acts as drainage or irrigation channel and path for appli-

- cation of plant protection chemicals, growth regulators etc.; and
 - the device simplifies placement of urea supergranules by applicator.
- The planting rod costs about US\$14.